

RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: ESSAIDI

FIRST NAME: MOHAMED

PROGRAM CODE: DIFE

COURSE CODE: ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 6

INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is the correct affirmation about plagiarism?
 - Plagiarism is quoting ideas without giving credit to their author.
 - Quotations and paraphrases can be used randomly unless credit is not given to the author.
 - Plagiarism is an unethical issue but also an academic offense that can be seriously punished.¹**
 - We should cite every idea for which we are not the author.
2. What is not correct about these rules of paraphrases use?
 - The paraphrase must be written using one's own words.

1. Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fifth Edition (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 34.

In a research dissertation, using more quotations than paraphrases is better.²

The paraphrase must be written using a style different from the author's one.

Even if the paraphrase is written differently from its origin, it should comply with its sense.

3. Which of these answers is the right order of research project steps?

The research question, hypotheses, data, analysis, and conclusions.³

The research question, data, hypotheses, analysis, and conclusions.

The research question, data, analysis, hypotheses, and conclusions.

The research question, hypotheses, analysis, data, and conclusions.

4. In which case should we quote more words than paraphrase ideas?

The words are from an authority you plan to rely on or challenge.

The words are strikingly original or so compelling that the quotation can frame the rest of your discussion.

The words express a claim that you disagree with, and to be fair, you want to state it exactly.

All of the above answers.⁴

5. What should not generally be presented in the dissertation introduction?

2. Cleenewerck and Gulma, 36.

3. Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th Edition (Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 23.

4. Turabian, 51.

- The research context.
 - The methodology and how the paper addresses the research question.
 - A suggestion for further research.**⁵
 - The hypotheses and claim.
6. What is the correct answer about the author-date style?
- In parenthetical citations, we use the author's name, the year, and the page number.**⁶
 - In the reference list entries, we do not remind of the publication year because it is already mentioned in the parenthetical citation.
 - In the reference list entries, we use only the last name as in the parenthetical citation.
 - There is a difference between the book's and journal article's parenthetical citation.
7. What is the correct answer about the notes-bibliography style?
- Information about the citation are put inside the text like the author-date style.
 - Rules of capitalization and italics are not present compared with the author-date style.
 - The parenthetical citation and the reference list entries are similarly documented.
 - Parenthetical citations can be either footnotes or endnotes.**⁷

5. Turabian, 110.

6. Turabian, 228.

7. Turabian, 160.

8. Which of the following documents is (are) not usually produced by an author of a dissertation research?

The dissertation concept paper and manuscript.⁸

The dissertation prospectus.

The dissertation.

The dissertation concept paper.

9. What is the right sequencing of these research milestones in the Ph.D. journey?

Research questions, literature review, variables, measures, treatment, and findings.

Literature review, research questions, variables, measures, treatment, and findings.⁹

Literature review, research questions, measures, variables, treatment, and findings.

Research questions, literature review, measures, variables, treatment, and findings.

10. Which of the following countries does not belong to the European Union member states?

Malta.

Latvia.

Slovenia.

8. James P Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 2.

9. Sampson, 19.

Liechtenstein.¹⁰

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024.

European Commission. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. Eighth Edition. European Union, 2021.

Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. 9th Edition. Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

10. European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, Eighth Edition (European Union, 2021), 96.